

IMPROVING PRODUCT QUALITY MANAGEMENT IN CONSTRUCTION ENTERPRISES (ON THE EXAMPLE OF SAMARKAND REGION)

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Introduction. Selecting the optimal technological process at the stage of preparation for production is a difficult and responsible task, as at this stage there is a constant need for technology and the need to improve the economic performance of production. Improving product quality at the stage of preparation is one of the main tasks of the enterprise. At the production stage, the following measures will be taken:

1. Direct production;
2. Ensuring and controlling the required level of quality of equipment, devices, control and measuring equipment;
3. Preparation and implementation of measures to improve product quality, prevent failure, eliminate the causes of non-compliance with regulatory documents;
4. Introduction of regulatory documents and strict adherence to them;
5. Establishment of access control of raw materials, materials, semi-finished

ABSTRACT

Product quality management systems ensure that technical development in the production process is at a constant high rate. For complex and responsible products, special work plans are developed in the process of quality management in production. Samples of new products can be produced in special design research or production institutes, industrial enterprises, design and technological departments (bureaus). In this case, the sample focus is on whether the product is really new or whether the product is in production. Opinions and comments on product quality are discussed at the event

products and components entering the enterprise;

6. Establish control over the operation, acceptance and testing of products;
7. Observance of inspection control, regulatory documents;
8. Collection and collection of information on the quality of the product at the stage of use, accounting and analysis of its invalidity, complaints about it;
9. Ensuring and controlling the movement of raw materials, semi-finished products, components and finished products in warehouses, on-site transport in accordance with the requirements of regulatory documents;
10. Material and moral incentives for employees of the enterprise in the production of products of a certain level of quality.

Provides product quality management systems in production associations, enterprises to achieve the goals and

objectives set at the production stage. The direction of management at the stages of transactions and sales will be focused on creating the necessary conditions for storage, transportation, sales in accordance with the planned tasks, standards and specifications. It is envisaged to follow the rules of loading and unloading of products in transport. The finished product should be protected from heat and other adverse effects during storage. At this stage, the quality of the finished product must be maintained at a high level and quality management systems ensure that it is delivered to the consumer in the specified quality indicators. To achieve these goals, the manufacturer takes the following measures:

1. Collection and processing and analysis of information on the use and storage of consumer goods and the degree of its compliance with the needs of the consumer;
2. Providing consumers with the necessary documents for operation and maintenance;
3. Warranty repair of products;
4. Providing consumers with spare parts, tools and manufactured goods.

Literature review. Quality systems are activities that cover all aspects of quality, provide all its aspects and cover all stages of the product life. Quality work begins in the field of marketing (market analysis and sales) and ends with the use of waste from the use of the product. The sum of these stages is called the quality ring, the definition of which is given above. Special requirements are placed on the methodological basis of product quality assessment in quality systems, especially in the mandatory and voluntary certification

of products, which provides almost the following:

1. The possibility of a comprehensive analysis and objective assessment of all consumer properties of the product, safety and environmental friendliness;
2. Based on the assessment, to create a basis for social protection of the consumer from the risks of use and environmental friendliness of the product, as well as from the risk of incorrect assessment of the product and its quality.

Differential method is a method of product quality assessment based on the use of a single indicator of product quality. The differential method is based on comparing the quality of the evaluated product with the underlying indicator. For example, the service life of equipment produced by one enterprise is 8 years, in another enterprise this figure is 12 years, and the base value is 10 years. the level of product quality is lower than the base value in the first enterprise, and higher in the second. This figure is due to the improvement of its service life.

Predicting, planning, and standardizing are important steps in improving product quality. Predicting product quality means determining the possible values of product quality indicators that can be degraded at a given time or in a given time interval. Product quality planning means setting a task for the production of a product based on the values of the required quality indicators within a given time or in a given period of time. Product quality management plays a special role in ensuring the quality of products. The essence of any management is the development of management decisions and their influence on the object of management. Product quality management

is a set of actions taken to ensure the required quality and consistency in the creation of a product. The quality of the product depends on how the processes are organized, how well they work, how well the control and measuring instruments work and the skills of the staff working in these processes. The effect of control is to maintain or modify the current state of the controlled processes. Product quality management system is a set of interaction of management agencies and controlled entities in the management of product quality with the help of logistics and information.

In short, the method of product quality assessment based on the use of complex indicators of product quality is called a complex method. For example, in the assessment of the quality of buses, the generalized quality indicator is their annual performance. In the mixed method, the quality of the product is assessed simultaneously using both single and complex indicators. Mathematical statistical methods are used to assess the quality of the product by the statistical method.

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